

TEACHING 2/3 YEAR-OLD CHILDREN WITH INTERACTIVE METHODS

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses instructing children in the age of 2/3 year-old through interactive methods. At this age, children are like little sponges, picking up every bit of information about the world around them. The majority of things that your two year old learns will be through play and normal social interaction. Everyday occurrences can provide numerous learning activities for your two year old. However, there are plenty of everyday skills and tasks that you can start teaching your toddler.

As a pediatric occupational therapist, I know that children can learn a significant amount of knowledge through their everyday play. Toys and gadgets may be teaching them things like cause-and-effect, problem solving, and new language. They will also be developing key skills like hand-eye coordination and independence. Both structured and unstructured play are important to develop these necessary skills. Most of what they learn, you won't even realize that you're teaching them! However, if you're not in the education field, you may be unsure of simple ways to teach your two year old or ways to incorporate new learning into everyday activities.

Below are a bunch of skills and concepts that you can help your 2-3 years old to understand. Practice and exposure is the best way to develop new skills with your child [1]. Below is a list of learning activities for two year old for the whole range up to 3. Not exclusively once they turn two. "Always remember that every child develops at their own pace so don't worry too much if your child doesn't know all of these concepts yet. This isn't a list of what they should know at this point, but rather a guide to help you understand what they may be capable of learning at this age" [2].

Your 2-year-old should have gained a slew of new vocabulary words in the past year. Now they're learning how to put these words together to form 2-3 word phrases, short sentences, and questions. Here are some of the common words, phrases, and concepts that your two-year old may be able to say and understand:

- Action words to help them communicate (more, go, come, want, up, down, etc.)
- Manners (please, thank you)
- Names of body parts (head, hand, nose, eyes,)
- Animal sounds and names of animals(moo, dog ,cat)

- Names (their own first and last name, and names of family and friends)
- Vehicles (cars, trucks, firetruck, airplane)
- Household objects (names of certain food, utensils, furniture, clothing, etc that they use daily)
- Colors and Shapes(red ,blue, pink)
- Sizes (big, small, tall, short)
- Direction words (below, above, next to, on top, underneath, etc. *although this may still develop more later*)
- Weather (sunny, rainy, cloudy, windy, snowy, hot, cold, etc.)

Before they turn 3, they should have a pretty extensive vocabulary. If your child has several words, help them to group words together if they're not doing so on their own. For example, if your child says "more," repeat after them, "more Cheerios?" and have them repeat the two words together. If they say, "want water," repeat after them, "I want water?" and have them repeat that as well. Adding on words to their current vocabulary will help them speak in longer phrases and sentences. If your child is not continuing to gain more words throughout the past few months, consult your pediatrician [3]. Here are more tips to get your toddler to talk here.

At 2, your child should definitely get the concept of "reading" a book. Of course, they won't actually be reading the words, but they will most likely grab a book and snuggle in the corner of the couch to flip through the pages. Make sure they understand how to read the book from front cover to back cover and the right way to hold it. They will simply look at the pictures at this age, but as they get later in their 2's, they'll start to recognize that there are letters and words on the page that actually mean something [4].

When you are reading to them, be sure to use your finger to follow along with the words on the page so they start to associate the letters with what you're saying. At this point, you can stop making up your own words or just describing the pictures on the page and actually read word-for-word. This way, your toddler will get the concept that a story is being told.

Have your toddler describe the pictures to you and you can even ask them questions about the pictures or the words that you just read?

Questions like, "What color is the girl's dress" or "Which one is bigger, the lion or the snail?" are appropriate at this age.

Children come in all shapes and sizes but development at 2-3 years typically has some things in common. Here is what might be happening for your child, how you can help, and when to see a child health professional for a qualified assessment.

This is one of your child's most important ages for emotional development. Your toddler is going through many emotions while also learning about other people's feelings. Tantrums are common, because your toddlers can't always communicate their needs. They often don't know how to put words to 'big' emotions. Your toddler is also starting to understand how their behaviour affects you and how your behaviour affects them. Your toddler might not get so upset when you leave them. But they'll still want a lot of your attention and might cling to you when they're tired or frightened – or just want a cuddle. Around 2 years, toddlers might be able to use sentences of 2-3 words and say 'I', 'you' and 'me'. Your toddler is learning and using a lot of words and might be easier to understand when

talking. At 3 years, toddlers can usually use sentences of 3-5 words, or even more. Your toddler starts learning how to take turns when speaking and might be able to have a short conversation with you. Your toddler is learning how to talk about things that have happened during the day. With your help, your toddler might be able to put things in order to make a simple story – for example, ‘I go shop’. ‘And what did you do at the shop?’ ‘Buy milk.’ By 3 years, your toddler might be able to tell a simple ‘made-up’ story based on their own experiences, but it will probably be quite short.

Everything toddlers have learned so far has developed their thinking. Your toddler is starting to understand concepts like time and opposites – for example, big/small and day/night. Your toddler is also starting to point to body parts based on what they do, sort objects, and match shapes and colours [5]. And your toddler is starting to remember what some things look like – for example, apples look red and round. Your toddler solves problems by trying things out.

Play is important because it is how children learn. Your toddler enjoys playing with others, playing dress-up, having tea parties, finger painting, and rough and tumble play. When your toddler plays with you or other children, you might find that your toddler is getting better at taking turns. Telling stories, singing and reading are also fun things for your toddler to do at this age.

Play is more than just fun for babies and children. It’s how they learn and develop. Playing with your child is one of the most important things you can do. Play is vital for your toddler’s cognitive development – that is, your toddler’s ability to think, understand, communicate, make memories, imagine and work out what might happen next [6]. This is because play is one of the main ways that your toddler explores the world. Toddlers at play are experimenting, thinking, solving problems and learning all the time. Spending time playing with your toddler is especially good for your toddler’s cognitive development. That’s because playing together builds your relationship and sends a simple but powerful message – you are important to me. This message is key to helping your toddler learn about who they are and where they fit in the world. It also gives your toddler confidence to keep exploring and learning about the world.

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